
Correlation of gamma glutamyl transpeptidase (γ GT) levels in patients with hepatitis and related chronic hepatic conditions

Junaid Mahmood Alam¹, Sana Anwar², Sarah Sughra Asghar³, Syed Riaz Mahmood⁴

¹Department of Biochemistry lab services and Chemical Pathology, Pakistan

²Department of Clinical Microbiology, Liaquat National Hospital and Medical College, Karachi. Pakistan.

³Department of Anatomy, Sir Syed Institute of Medical Sciences. Karachi, Pakistan

⁴Got Lyari General hospital, Karachi. Pakistan

Abstract Gamma glutamyl transpeptidase (abbreviated as γ GT) is a notable hepatic enzyme that plays an important role in gamma-glutamyl cycle in liver. Any alterations in its concentration depict patho-physiological changes or a diseased condition in liver. The current study describes the assessment of correlation of elevated γ GT levels with hepatitis stages and/or related chronic conditions such as hepatoma, to evaluate its diagnostic significance. One hundred and sixty patients (males n = 102; females n = 58) within age range of 27-76 yrs were selected retrospectively for the period Dec 2015 to Dec 2017, and when required prospectively through evaluation of laboratory information system. The evaluated clinical status of hepatitis, with progressing clinical conditions, was classified into four stages I-IV. Blood samples were analyzed for γ GT, ALT (alanine aminotransferase), AST (aspartate aminotransferase), ALP (alkaline phosphatase), Bil (Total bilirubin), albumin, (ALB) Pro-thrombin time (PT) and hepatitis profile tests by standard methods. Cumulative correlation of γ GT with all four hepatitis stages depicted significant correlation of $R^2 = 0.958$ whereas corresponding significant linearity manifested as R^2 of 0.927 in individual staging I, $R^2 = 0.885$ in stage II, $R^2 = 0.972$ in Stage III and $R^2 = 0.972$ in Stage IV. γ GT exhibited around 3 folds ($P < 0.01$) increase at stage I, 19 folds ($P < 0.00001$) at stage IV when compared with controls, and upto 7 folds when γ GT levels of stage I were compared with levels of Stage IV ($P < 0.0001$) of the same. The significance of γ GT was further strengthened when γ GT levels were compared with other hepatic parameters including ALT, AST, ALP, Bil, ALB and PT with intensifying degree of elevation at initial and various progressing stages of hepatitis. The results showed that γ GT is the most significantly independent hepatic parameter that exhibited significant elevation at all hepatitis stages in comparison with other hepatic parameters. The presented data sturdily suggested substantial significance of determining γ GT in hepatic infections and recommend inclusion of it in assessments of patients that were suspected of or confirmed with progressing clinical severity such as development of end stage cirrhosis and even malignancy to conclude better prognosis and adjustments of treatment regiments.

Keywords Gamma glutamyl transpeptidase, γ GT, hepatitis, Hepatic parameters

1. Introduction

Gamma glutamyl transferase or gamma glutamyl transpeptidase (abbreviated as γ GT) is a notable hepatic enzyme bearing the nomenclature of EC 2.3.2.2 and involved in transfer of gamma-glutamyl functional groups [1]. Since it

plays an important role in gamma-gutamyl cycle in liver, which is the main metabolic pathway for glutathione, in addition to drugs detoxications cycles, any alterations in its concentration depicts patho-physiological changes or a diseased condition in liver [1,2]. In most of hepatic diseases, including hepatitis and cirrhosis, elevation of γ GT was often reported, that depicted parenchymal damages and eventual poor response to therapy [3-6]. In recent years, γ GT has also been indicated as a biomarker for evaluation of chronic hepatic conditions, such as hepatitis C and B infections and in some cases, HCC [2,4, 7-9]. The current study describes the assessment of correlation of elevated γ GT levels with hepatitis stages and/or related chronic conditions such as hepatoma, to evaluate its diagnostic significance for prognosis and treatments.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Research protocols and patients selection: The current research study covers the period of Dec 2015 to Dec 2017. Patients were selected through retrospective, and when required prospective evaluation of laboratory information system, counseling of patients attending lab and out-door services and data review. It was ensured that only those patients' data were included that were assigned with hepatitis anomalies. All data gathered, inclusive of hepatic profiles, hepatitis status and laboratory findings were grouped accordingly as per protocols described earlier [10]. Initial assessments of data was carried out in 520 patients, that were further merited through evaluation and investigations into final number of 160 patients (males $n = 102$; females $n = 58$) within age range of 27-76 yrs. To determine and establish proper correlation between γ GT and hepatitis status, the clinical conditions were classified into four stages I-IV as per description detailed in a recent study [10]. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were also established accordingly, keeping in view related co-morbid and interfering components. Patients were grouped according to their stages as Stage I, $n = 31$; Stage II, $n = 35$; Stage III, $n = 55$ and Stage IV, $n = 39$.

2.2. Sample collection and chemical analysis: Blood samples were collected for analysis of γ GT, ALT (alanine aminotranferase), AST (aspartate aminotranferase), ALP (alkaline phosphatase), Bil (Total bilirubin), albumin, (ALB) Pro-thrombin time (PT), hepatitis profile tests by standard methods ALT (alanine aminotranferase) and hepatitis profile tests. Hepatic profile testing was performed on Axsym (Abbott, USA) whereas γ GT, ALT AST, ALP, Bil and albumin were analyzed by IFCC (international federation of clinical chemists) recommended method on Cobas 6000 c501 (Roche Diagnostics, Basil), where as PT was analyzed on CA-1500 (Sysmex). During initial analysis and data collection, it was observed that there were no significant difference or variation among above mentioned hepatic parameters in both hepatitis B or C patients and even males and females, thus data were combined together as a single entity for broader balanced assessment. Normal reference range for ALT is less than 40 IU/L, γ GT = 32- 49 IU/L, AST = 35-50 IU/L, ALP = 104-129 IU/L, Bil = less than 1.0 mg/dl, Alb = 3.4-4.8 gm/dl and PT = 8-12 seconds.

Hepatitis staging I t IV, Inclusion and Exclusion criteria: The stages were designated according to clinical and lab profile data. Stage I = Hepatitis C or B reactive + fatty liver seen, stage II = hepatitis C or B reactive + cirrhosis [non-invasive]; stage III = hepatitis C or B highly reactive + with CT/X ray described cirrhosis progression; stage IV = Hepatitis C or B highly reactive + highly progressive/ proliferative cirrhosis or/and hepatoma. Patients with previous history of surgery, immuno-compromised, known alcoholics, steroidal therapies, below 20 years and above 80 yrs were excluded from the study.

Statistical analysis: Data were statistically analyzed by Pearson's correlation, multivariate analysis with level of significance $P < 0.05$ and regression R2 analysis by SPSS version 13 (USA).

3. Results

A total of 160 patients (males = 102 and females 58) were assessed for correlation of their γ GT levels in four stages of progression of hepatitis. Results are summarized in Fig 1 to Fig 5 and Table 1. During preliminary analysis of collected data, it was observed that there were no significant difference among all tested hepatic parameters such as γ GT, AST, ALT, ALP, Bil, Alb and PT in both hepatitis B or C patients of both genders, thus data were pooled together as a single entity for broader-based assessment. γ GT levels considerably corresponded to the stage of hepatitis from I to IV, which depicted moderate infection level (Stage I) to significantly morbid/critical stage of

hepatitis (Stage IV). Regression association analysis suggested linear correlation of γ GT levels and its corresponding relation to the hepatitis criticality. Cumulative correlation of γ GT with all hepatitis stages depicted significant correlation of $R^2 = 0.958$ (Fig 1) whereas corresponding significant linearity manifested as R^2 of 0.927 in individual staging I (Fig 2), $R^2 = 0.885$ (Fig 3) in stage II, $R^2 = 0.972$ (Fig 4) in Stage III and $R^2 = 0.972$ (Fig 5) in Stage IV. To further strengthen the resulting significant correlation of γ GT at various clinical stages of hepatitis, other hepatic parameters, such as ALT, AST, ALP, Bil, albumin and PT were included in the study and statistically analyzed with corresponding levels of γ GT (Table 1). The data suggested correlated significance of γ GT with other hepatic parameters, most significantly at Stage I levels of it with Alb, Bil and PT ($P < 0.001$) and stage II value with ALT, AST and ALP levels at stage IV ($P < 0.0001$). The elevation of γ GT was noted to be profound, a significant 3 folds ($P < 0.001$) at Stage I as compared control reference and 2 folds higher than other hepatic parametric elevations. Similarly, in comparison to control reference, a staggering 19 fold elevation ($P < 0.00001$) of γ GT level was noted in stage IV, a highly significant 7 fold ($P < 0.0001$) increase when stage IV levels were compared with stage I levels and 3 folds ($P < 0.001$) when stage I was compared with control reference values. Furthermore, when γ GT value of Stage IV was compared with ALT and AST of same staging, γ GT value were noted to 5-9 fold ($P < 0.0001$) higher than that of both hepatic enzymes (Table 1).

Table 1: γ -Glutamyl transpeptidase and other Hepatic parameters in patients of various Hepatitis stage

Hepatic parameters	Hepatitis stages				Control reference ranges
	I	II	III	IV	
γ GT IU/L	159.63 \pm 10.50 ^b	348.54 \pm 30.25 ^c	542.58 \pm 50.15	967.41 \pm 62.35 ^d	32-49 ^{b,c,d}
ALT IU/L	54.54 \pm 5.60 ^a	235.75 \pm 25.70	368.62 \pm 36.52	575.14 \pm 50.20 ^c	< 40 ^{a,c}
AST IU/L	52.46 \pm 5.90	213.80 \pm 16.70 ^a	396.75 \pm 32.65	490.29 \pm 48.25 ^c	35-50 ^{a,c}
ALP IU/L	168.25 \pm 15.20 ^a	259.46 \pm 26.15	401.25 \pm 35.60	509.30 \pm 51.35 ^c	104-129 ^{a,c}
Bil mg/dl	2.26 \pm 0.95 ^a	5.20 \pm 1.10	4.29 \pm 0.98	4.90 \pm 1.10 ^b	< 1.0 ^b
Alb gm/dl	3.90 \pm 0.86	3.50 \pm 0.60	3.00 \pm 0.50	2.90 \pm 0.40 ^b	3.4-4.8 ^b
PT sec	12.40 \pm 1.25	13.26 \pm 2.40	15.29 \pm 3.50	16.31 \pm 4.60 ^b	8-12 ^b

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD

γ GT (γ -Glutamyl transpeptidase), ALT (alanine aminotransferase), AST (aspartate aminotransferase), ALP (alkaline phosphatase), Bil (Total bilirubin), albumin, (ALB) Pro-thrombin time (PT).

Statistical analysis = $P < 0.05$ level of significance. **a** = 0.01, **b** = 0.001, **c** = 0.0001, **d** = 0.00001

4. Discussion

Previous and recent past studies have reported significant elevation of γ GT in HCV-infected patients and in some cases HCC [2-4,7-9,11,12]. In our study considerable correlation was depicted by γ GT with various stages of hepatitis from $R^2 = 0.885$ to $R^2 = 0.972$ with cumulative R^2 of 0.95. Similarly when γ GT was compared with other hepatic parameters, significant correlation was noted regarding intensity of γ GT elevation at various hepatitis stages and levels of significance with ALT, AST, ALP, Alb and PT. Association of elevated γ GT levels and various advanced stages of hepatic fibrosis 3 and 4 was reported earlier [10,11,13]. It was argued that chronic infections of B and C origin and subsequent histological damage may represent corresponding elevation of γ GT and ALT levels [5-7,14,15]. More recent studies suggested a positive role of γ GT, along with alpha-fetoprotein (AFP) and interleukin 18 in evaluation of HCC [3]. Furthermore, not only hepatic disorders, diabetes mellitus, when remained untreated, were also noted as one of the co-morbid for instigating γ GT elevation, suggesting stressing of hepatic metabolic functions [9]. Previous studies by several clinicians also considered γ GT as a significant and independent marker in patients with hepatitis B and C infections [5,16-18], advocating our study, that depicted high level of γ GT in patients with hepatitis C infections and progressing cirrhotic or malignant conditions.

5. Conclusion

The present study described determination of γ GT levels in patients of various mild and chronic stages of hepatitis infections. γ GT significantly correlated with different progressing clinical stages of I to IV of hepatitis with regression correlation generation of R^2 0.885 to 0.972. The data strongly suggested considerable significance of estimation of γ GT in hepatic infections and in progressing clinical severity of chronic cirrhosis and development of malignancy such as HCC for recommending better prognosis and adjustments of treatment regimens.

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